

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Duck

Level: Transportation

Keywords: Handling

Background context provided by the requestor

This query concerns the recommended methods for duck catching, their advantages and disadvantages in terms of traumatism and other lesions at the slaughterhouse (ante- and post-mortem inspection).

Questions raised by the requestor

Q1: Does catching ducks (more than 7 days of age) by the neck induce pain, handling stress and injuries?

Q2: What are the optimal methods of catching ducks (more than 7 days of age) that minimize the risk of pain, stress and injury to the birds?

Answer

Introduction

Although domestication and subsequent genetic selection of poultry have reduced the magnitude of their handling stress, poultry still perceive humans as predators (Gerritzen and Raj, 2009; EFSA, 2022) and birds can show moderate adverse effects (e.g. higher plasma corticosterone concentrations) from catching (example in laying hens: Gerpe et al., 2021). In particular, fear responses are characteristic from the domestic duck, showing significant vigilance behaviour and flight response to humans or non-human objects (e.g. herding robots, vehicles, model of a fox or cylinders) being reported (Henderson et al., 2000, 2001; EFSA, 2023).

Handling birds may cause fear and/or pain (due to injuries due to escape attempts) if the methods used are not appropriate for the species concerned. Handling/catching stress indicates that the animals experience stress and/or negative affective states such as fear resulting from human or mechanical handling (EFSA, 2022). Even if the duration of the handling is limited, the welfare consequences can persist throughout the entire transport operation. In ducks, poor catching and handling can lead to fear and pain due to injuries, leading for example to lameness, especially because catching them by the leg may lead to hip dislocation (HSA, 2025).

Q1: Does catching ducks by the neck induce pain, handling stress and injuries?

Catching and handling of poultry, whatever the method, are generally recognized to cause fear and distress (Gerritzen and Raj, 2009). Catching methods should be adapted to the characteristics of the bird species being handled. According to EFSA (2022), whatever the species, domestic birds should be carried upright by holding the wings against the body and not inverted or by their neck or wings. In the EU Factsheet about "how to handle and restrain poultry" it is stated never try to move a bird by lifting/dragging by the neck/head/wing/tail (European Union, 2018).

No references describing the negative consequences of catching ducks by the neck have been found. However, as for all domestic birds, handling is a stressful event for ducks. Catching ducks by the neck while supporting their body weight and without obstructing the windpipe is not expected to injure or cause pain to the bird. In contrast, lifting ducks solely by the neck is likely to cause handling stress and pain due to neck supporting all the body weight and this could lead to injuries in neck tissues including in the trachea and/or suffocation (according to EURCAW expert's opinion).

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Q2: What are the optimal methods of catching ducks that minimize the risk of pain, stress and injury to the birds?

When carrying ducks, the weight of the bird body must be supported either by a hand or arm placed under its body, or by holding the bird with a hand on either side of its body with the wings in the closed position (Figure 1) (Defra, 2002; HSA, 2018; RSPCA, 2023). According to RSPCA (2023) guidance, ducks must not be carried: hanging head downwards, by the legs, by the wing(s), by the head, by the tail or by the neck. However, it can be recommended to gently lift the duck by the base of the neck for a minimal time, without applying excessive pressure, before transferring the bird to the catcher's hands and arms. Holding briefly by the base of neck minimizes flapping and therefore reduces injury (HSA, 2018). In addition, if ducks are lifted by the base of neck, care must be taken to ensure the bird's windpipe is not likely to be obstructed and the movement should be smooth and gentle, without sudden change in direction (RSPCA, 2023). Once the weight of the animal is supported by the hand/arm, controlling the legs with the fingers is recommended to control the bird if it wriggles or scratches, and the wings can then be controlled by the opposite hand or by holding the bird against the operator's body, under the arm (HSA, 2025). Since the legs are weak, catching of carry ducks by the legs will easily cause disjointed or broken legs (Defra, 2002; Clauer and Skinner, 2007; HSA, 2018; RSPCA, 2023).

Figure 1. The weight of the bird body must always be supported either by a hand or arm placed under its body (image from HSA, 2025)

Conclusions

Catching and handling of poultry, whatever the method, are generally recognized to cause negative affective states such as fear or pain. No references describing the negative consequences of catching ducks specifically by the neck have been found. However, catching ducks by the neck while supporting their body weight and without obstructing the windpipe is not expected to cause injury or cause pain to the bird. In contrast, lifting ducks solely by the neck is likely to cause handling stress and pain, considering their body weight, and it could lead to injuries in the trachea or other neck tissues or suffocation. To prevent this, when carrying ducks, the weight of the bird must be supported either by taking the body of the bird by a hand or arm placed under its body, or by holding the bird with a hand on either side of its body with the wings in the closed position.

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Co-funded by
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